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“BIOMASS WASTES AS NUTRITIVE MATERIAL FOR EFFICIENT PRODUCTION OF BIOGAS”

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Abstract

In Jaipur city we have a famous juice centre at Gopalpura i.e Girnar Juice Centre. It offers various types of juices of wide variety of fruits such as chikoo, papaya, mango, watermelon, pineapple etc. A large amount of fruit waste is collected at this Juice shop, which can be further utilized for the production of biogas. Mean while a big challenge has been faced by the solid waste management authority like municipality, especially fruit waste i.e generated in large amount per day. This work has two aspects one is the management of such huge generation and another is the production of energy in terms of Biogas and optimization of bio gas generated from these waste. Biogas production requires anaerobic digestion .My research work was to create an Organic Processing Facility to create biogas which will be more cost effective, eco-friendly, cut down on landfill waste, generate a high-quality renewable fuel, and reduce carbon dioxide & methane emissions. It is Green technology energy source, Zero waste technology. There was a digester tank of capacity 20 litre for decomposition of cow dung slurry and fruit waste. Two chemicals that is Na_2CO_3 and NaOH was used to make the buffer solution. Urea was added to increase the production of biogas. The fruit waste is grinded properly in grinding machine so that the surface area of slurry is increased and material will easily decompose in short time. Physio-chemical parameters of these influent (on the starting day of digestion) and effluent slurries (after 30th day from starting) in terms of total solid, volatile solid, temperature, pH and Non volatile solid were tested.

Overall study reveals that ideal condition for the production of bio gas is that pH of influent slurry must be 5.7 which was obtain by using buffering chemicals and waste should be grinded properly so that they decompose easily. This work can solve the problems of kitchen waste management as well as bring the fulfilment of energy requirement in terms of Biogas and optimization of biogas.

INTRODUCTION

India is a heavily populated country and this is the only reason for enormous waste that is being produced regularly out of household & industrial activities like peeling and cutting of raw Fruit and Vegetable Waste prior to processing, eating, and cooking. Serious environmental and health problems are related to inadequate solid waste disposal. Garbage dumped in open places cause heavy pollution due to soil, ground water and surface waters [1, 2]. Fruit Vegetable Waste is generally stale or spoilt, not fit for human consumption. These materials are usually high in fibre content and are of different sizes and forms. Fruit and Vegetable Wastes have a high moisture content of 80-89%. Three fourth of the total solids present are volatile solids. Their biodegradability varies accordingly with the state of hardening and kind of waste material. Carbon to nitrogen ratio varies in each vegetable, however for mixed variety it may be around 1:20 to 1:30. The origin of biogas is traced back to the Persians. They discovered that organic matter such as rotting vegetables gave a flammable gas that could be used for other purposes. Anaerobic digestion of sorted organic wastes from municipal solid waste (MSW) especially food waste is a cost effective technology [3, 4].

Methane fermentation is a complex process. The general process of anaerobic digestion is a series of processes like enzymatic hydrolysis, acid genesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis [5] and each metabolic stage is assisted by a series of micro organisms. Amongst the four stages, hydrolysis is the rate limiting stage for FVW [6,7].

Hydrolysis:-

Acidogenesis:-

Acetogenesis:-

Methanogenesis:-

Biogas

Biogas is generated when bacteria degrade biological material in the absence of oxygen, in a process known as anaerobic digestion. Since biogas is a mixture of methane (also known as marsh gas or natural gas, CH₄) and carbon dioxide it is a renewable fuel produced from waste treatment. Anaerobic digestion is basically a simple process carried out in a number of steps that can use almost any organic

material as a substrate - it occurs in digestive systems, marshes, rubbish dumps, and septic tanks. Conventional anaerobic digestion has been a "liquid" process, where waste is mixed with water to facilitate digestion, but a "solid" process is also possible, as occurs in landfill sites.

There are many advantages of biogas over wood as a cooking fuel:-

- Trees can be retained.
- Biogas is a quick, easily controlled fuel.
- No smoke or smell so reduced eye/respiratory irritation.
- Sludge is a better fertiliser than manure or synthetic fertilisers (and is cheaper than manufactured products).
- Reduced pathogen transmission compared to untreated waste.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection & preparation of sample

Fruit wastes have been collected from Girnar Juice Centre at Gopalpura and also collected from regular household activities like peeling and cutting prior to cooking. These wastes included peels and wastes portions of and fruits. They have been subjected to sun drying for 4 to 5 days followed by grinding to form fine powdered waste and passed through standard size reduction equipment for a particular particle size and finally stored in container for use in anaerobic digestion process.

Methods

All experiments have been performed in 20L batch digesters essentially made of plastic. A set of 1 digester have been used at a time for experimentation. The following parameters of biogas production were calculated using various equipments.

1. pH of the Sample
2. Temperature
3. Total solid
 - ✓ Total solid of inlet slurry.
 - ✓ Total solid of out let slurry.
4. Non volatile solid
 - ✓ Non volatile solid of inlet slurry.
 - ✓ Non volatile solid of outlet slurry.
4. Volume of gas

Equipments to be used:-

1. Water Tank
2. Pipe
3. T- Valve
4. gas Valve

- 5. Funnel
- 6. Tyre Tube

Work plan:-

Biogas Plant is settled as shown in the above picture. The digester tank is painted black. Due to the transparency of the digester tank light will penetrate into the tank. If the light penetrates in to the digester tank algae will be produced. Production of algae leads to the development of oxygen which makes the bacteria respire aerobically, thus the process in anaerobic. Due to anaerobic action methane gas will be produced and thus the temperature of the mixture will be maintained.

Later on in the 10 litre water we mix 100 grams of urea. Fruit waste of 4 Kg is collected and is chopped into pieces. All the materials i.e. 5 Kg cow dung, 4 Kg Fruit waste, 100 grams of urea and 10 litre water is mixed well in the tub. After mixing the ingredients in the tub they are poured in the digester tank. This slurry is poured into the digester tank using funnel and a small amount of sample is kept for performing the test. The digester tank is made air tight with the help of sealants and is kept for 30 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After 30 days we see that our tube is filled with biogas completely and gas is burns with brown flame. Various parameters of inlet and outlet of slurry is as follows:-

Parameters	pH	Temperature	Total solid	Volatile solid	Non Volatile solid
Inlet	5.7	290C	73.07%	88.24%	11.76%
Outlet	4.8	310 C	24.76%	87.50%	12.50%

Experimental details/Observation

S.No.	Time	Sample appearance	Evolution of gas	Ignition of Gas	Smell	Volume of Gas (m ³)
1	Day 1	Biogas produced is half the volume of container.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.530
2	Day 5	The Biogas that is produced fills the container completely.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.627
3	Day 10	The Biogas that is produced fills the container completely.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.704
4	Day 15	The Biogas that is produced fills the container completely.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.756
5	Day 20	The Biogas that is produced fills the container completely.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.816
6	Day 25	The Biogas that is produced fills the container completely.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.896
7	Day 30	The Biogas that is produced fills the container completely.	It feels by hand that temperature of digester rises slowly.	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.952

Fig. Volume of Gas (m³)/Days

Fig. Biogas Material in %

Table: pH

Table: Temperature

Fig. Quantity of Material in %

CONCLUSION

Present study provides information about the useful utilization of Fruit Waste by anaerobic digestion process for the production of biogas. Study shows that how yield of biogas have been enhanced by the addition of urea and thereby how a kinetic model has been used to validate the yield of biogas being obtained. Certain process parameters have been found to be more effective than one another like slurry concentration, catalyst concentration and temperature. These parameters have been verified by the evaluated kinetic parameters that justify the optimum conditions for maximum yield of biogas.

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